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ABSTRACT

Machine Learning (ML) techniques have been widely used both in science and industry for discovery purposes and for predictions from data. The applications range from High Energy Physics experiments or biological studies to speech recognition or natural language processing and text analytics. Recently, ML methods are gaining interest in the particle accelerator and beam instrumentation community. Task 10.6 has explored the potential of ML-based systems for identifying early signs of errant beam conditions in real-time. This document is the final deliverable of the task and summarizes the acquisition and analysis of ESS commissioning data as well as the development of data workflows and a low latency platform suitable for the training and implementation of real-time ML algorithms at ESS and other high-power accelerator facilities.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

Building upon the intermediate report delivered for Milestone 48[1], this report is the final deliverable of I.FAST Task 10.6 that focussed on the application of low-latency Machine Learning (ML) at the European Spallation Source (ESS). Task 10.6 explored the potential of ML-based systems to identify errant beam conditions in real-time and assert triggers to acquire detailed data or even remove beam permit with the ultimate goal of improving the performance and availability of high-power hadron accelerators.

Equipped with a variety of beam instrumentation systems, the ESS linear accelerator provided the data for this study. Since most of the data was acquired during 2023 commissioning of the normal-conducting linac, the report describes the experience with the tools available at this time as well as the improvements based on the lessons learned. Improvements include a Synchronous Data Service that complements the enhanced Archiver Appliance to provide detailed data structures from nominal as well as anomalous pulses. These tools are part of an overarching data framework that that will support data-intensive AI applications.

A low latency architecture suitable for real-time ML algorithms has also been developed. The Polish Ministry of Science and the ESS project are now supporting the realization of this architecture at a scale suitable for the whole of the ESS accelerator. The platform utilizes Field-programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) to process signals, transport them and apply ML algorithms.

Results of clustering studies on signals from beam current, position and phase signals are presented. While shape discrimination has been demonstrated, robust identification of precursors to anomalous beam will require more data from stable operations. Looking forward to full deployment of the low-latency platform, the toolchain to implement relevant algorithms on the selected Versal FPGA was assessed. With commissioning of the entire ESS linac commencing during Spring 2025, the collaborators now well positioned with tools for data acquisition, analysis, and ML implementation. They expect to have a positive impact not only on ESS, but also on high power hadron facilities in Europe and beyond.

1 Introduction and Motivation

Rapid start-up and reliable operation of a particle accelerator requires a diverse suite of beam instrumentation systems for the monitoring and characterization of the beam. Additionally, some of these systems provide protection functions that detect potentially damaging beam conditions and remove beam permit before damage occurs. Complex simulations of beam dynamics and beam-material interactions can determine which beam conditions are damaging. However, such an approach requires detailed knowledge of all relevant failure scenarios and usually depend upon measurements that may be virtually impossible to obtain in real time.

Alternatively, ML (Machine Learning) techniques can learn from examples without requiring explicit physical rules or modelling, thus offering a system-agnostic approach to detecting the onset of failures [2][3][4]. The relevant techniques fall into the category of anomaly detection, which along with optimization and modelling represent the broad AI (Artificial Intelligence) areas recently pursued by the particle accelerator community[5] [6][7]. I.FAST Task 10.6 explored the potential of low-latency ML techniques to improve performance and availability of high-power hadron accelerators with particular application to the proton linear accelerator (linac) at the European Spallation Source (ESS) in Lund, Sweden. The idea is to apply ML predictive techniques to large amounts of data from beam instrumentation systems and develop a data-driven model capable of real-time identification of beam conditions that can lead to beam induced damage. Depending on the outcome of this identification, the system may issue a request for data capture, operator intervention, or automatic correction. In severe cases, the beam production could be automatically inhibited. For a pulsed linac, these decisions need to be made on an interpulse (<71 ms in case of ESS) or intrapulse (<2.86 ms in case of ESS) timescales. This requires a platform that provides low-latency processing based on signals transported from the entire accelerator, also with minimum latency.

To execute the work of Task 10.6, a core team from ESS collaborated with staff from across the project to configure beam instrumentation systems and acquire detailed data from virtually every beam pulse during two commissioning runs. An archiver facility provided the persistent data store for the beam measurements and other relevant parameters. With collaborators from Riga Technical University (RTU), the data was extracted, cleaned and analysed with ML algorithms. Section 3 describes the data workflow along with ongoing improvements to the underlying tools, and Section 5 covers the application of ML algorithms. In parallel with the data analysis efforts, a team from ESS and the Warsaw University of Technology (WUT) developed the low latency platform based on Field-programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), assessed deployment techniques for ML models on the selected FPGA technology, and with assistance from Cosylab, will implement a subset of the models on FPGAs. Sections 4 and 6 describe this work.

2 ESS Accelerator and Instrumentation

2.1 THE LINAC

The ESS, which is currently being built in Lund, Sweden, will be a material science research facility[8][9]. Once constructed, it will become Europe’s leading facility for neutron-based research. The neutron production will be based on bombardment of a rotating tungsten target with a proton beam of 5 MW average power and macro-pulse beam current of 62.5 mA. A linac will accelerate protons to 2 GeV and transport them towards the target through a sequence of normal-conducting (NC) and superconducting (SC) accelerating structures (see Figure 1). The NC linac (NCL) consists of an ion source, Low Energy Beam Transport (LEBT), Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ), Medium Energy Beam Transport (MEBT) and Drift Tube Linac (DTL) sections. Beyond these sections, Spoke, Medium Beta and High Beta elliptical cavities together with High Energy Beam Transfer (HEBT) line comprise the SC linac (SCL).

Figure 1: Layout of the ESS linac. Red and blue colour mark the NC and SC parts of the linac, respectively

The accelerating structures operate at 352.21 MHz and 704.42 MHz frequencies in the upstream and downstream sections, respectively. During neutron production beam, the accelerator delivers beam to the target in 2.86 ms long pulses with a repetition rate of 14 Hz, corresponding to a duty cycle of 4%. During linac tuning and commissioning activities, the pulse length, repetition rate and pulse current can reach values below 5 μ s, 1 Hz and 6 mA, respectively.

2.2 RELEVANT PROTON BEAM INSTRUMENTATION

The full complement of ESS beam instrumentation includes over 500 systems of about 20 different types distributed throughout the linac, transport lines and target station[10]. The following sections describe the specific systems that already provided data for this ML study or are expected to provide data during the upcoming commissioning runs. The Beam Current Monitor (BCM) and the Beam Position Monitor (BPM) provided nearly all of the measurements used in the studies so far, and as such, these systems are described in more detail than the others. Given that most of the measurements were taken during stability runs of the NCL, the relevant systems are the non-invasive instruments located in this part of the ESS linac. In the future, similar ML studies will include data from instrumentation located downstream in both the SCL and the target station.

2.2.1 Beam Current Monitors

The ESS Beam Current Monitor (BCM) system includes in total 19 AC Current Transformers (ACCTs) and one Fast Current Transformer (FCT) which are all from Bergoz[11][12] Ten of these

ACCTs are installed in the NCL that extends from the Ion Source (ISrc) to the DTL tank 5. These sensors provide current measurement in the LEBT, MEBT and between the DTL tanks. The other nine ACCTs are installed in the Linac Warm Units (LWUs) in between the cryomodules in the Super Conducting Linac (SCL) and in the downstream sections. The FCT is installed at the end of the MEBT, and it is mainly used for verifying the beam pulse after the MEBT chopper.

The analogue signal from each ACCT is buffered and amplified by a wall-mount Front End (FE) module from Bergoz, and then low-pass filtered and further processed in a custom designed Back End (BE) unit in the BCM rack. The signal is then digitized and FPGA processed by a Struck SIS8300-KU board in a MicroTCA (MTCA) crate. The digital signal processing includes baseline restoration, droop compensation, digital filtering, post mortem data buffering as well as a complete suite of machine protection functions that are tailored to meet the ESS beam and machine requirements[13]. Part of these functions are used to measure the amplitude, width and repetition frequency of the beam pulse and send a beam abort request to the Fast Beam Interlock System (FBIS) within 1 μ s if the measured values exceed their thresholds. The BCM firmware configures the machine protection functions including the levels and activation/deactivation of the thresholds based on a beam mode and a beam destination ID that are distributed over the ESS network before starting with beam. Time windows for the expected beam pulses from the ISrc and LEBT/MEBT choppers are generated by the BCM firmware using the timing events that are distributed by the ESS Timing System (TS) over an optical fibre network at well-defined times before the arrival of each pulse. These time windows are then used for measuring the beam properties including average beam current over a region of interest and pulse length/charge. The BCM firmware also checks the exact timing of the TS events for any inconsistency with the selected beam mode due to possible bugs in the timing tables, human errors etc. This feature mitigates damage due to a wrong trigger length/frequency resulting in excessive beam power on a temporary beam dump. Other protection functions include differential beam interlocks with several BCM pairs, errant beam detection and BCM internal checks.

Figure 2: Simplified schematics showing the interconnections of the ACCT toroids, the AIU and the MTCA crate with the control group BCM-01 (i.e. from the ISRC to the DTL tank 2).

Figure 3: A low current beam pulse measured by eight BCMs from the LEBT to the DTL tank 4

The analogue ACCT signals are converted to digital with a sample rate of 88 MSPS. The raw data is then low-level processed in the BCM FPGA and decimated with a configurable decimation factor which is set to 16 by default. The resultant processed data with a sample rate of 5.5 MSPS is then converted to Experimental Physics and Industrial Control System (EPICS) Process Variables (PV) in the BCM Input-Output Controller (IOC) together with the raw data and published on the ESS network with a maximum update rate of 14 Hz. The data is then made available to the end user through the Machine-Expert and Engineering user interfaces.

The differential interlocks include several ACCT pairs with the two sensor signals ending up in one MTCA crate or two separate ones. In the latter cases, optical fibres are used to send BCM processed data from one MTCA crate to another. The existing FW support data from max two ACCTs being sent out on the same fibre in opposite directions using multi-mode OM4 fibres and the Xilinx Aurora 8b10b protocol.

The BCM FBIS interface consists of 4 LVDS channels (i.e. 3 discrete and 1 Manchester-encoded datalink) on the BCM digitizer board. A custom-designed interface module then converts the signals to RS-485 for improved noise immunity before sending the signals over long-haul cables to the FBIS unit. The discrete channels transmit the BCM Beam Permit, Ready and Beam Exist signals while the datalink sends the same information for redundancy as well as the selected Beam Mode, Beam Destination, MTCA crate ID and Life Sign Counter with a sample rate of 15.6 MSPS.

The BCM Post-Mortem includes a configurable ring buffer that keeps the most recent BCM data with a sample rate of 88 MSPS from all the channels and freezes the buffer contents as soon as the Beam Permit changes to NOK. During the beam on DTL4 FC commissioning run, the buffer size was set to 1.1 GB that is equivalent to 1 s of BCM data (i.e. 400 ms before plus 600 ms after a beam trip). The data is then written to a shared drive on the ESS technical network upon a beam trip. The operator can then load the data and plot the beam waveforms using Python scripts. This feature proved to be very useful in analysing the root cause of the beam trips by the BCM, and it helped to improve the beam availability. The Synchronous Data Service described in Section 3.4 will eventually provide similar capability to all systems.

2.2.2 Beam Position Monitors

The Beam Position Monitoring (BPM) system is responsible for measuring the longitudinal beam phase, the horizontal and vertical beam positions within the vacuum chamber, and the amplitude of a selected radio-frequency (RF) harmonic of interest—generally, the first harmonic in the SCL and the second harmonic in the NCL. The entire accelerator is equipped with 99 BPM systems, one of which is specifically designated for high-bandwidth measurements within the MEBT section[14].

Each BPM system provides diagnostic information on both transverse and longitudinal beam properties. The system captures four primary waveforms within a beam pulse window that can vary between approximately 5 μ s and 2.86 ms, operating at an update rate of 5.87 MHz. These waveforms correspond to the horizontal (x) and vertical (y) beam positions, the amplitude of a selected RF harmonic, and the beam phase. These parameters are computed in real-time by a custom FPGA firmware, which employs the near IQ-sampling algorithm **Error! Reference source not found.** The BPM signal processing architecture enables access to 19 waveforms per BPM at various stages of the digital signal processing (DSP) pipeline, including:

- **Raw data waveforms** from each individual antenna, sampled at 88 MHz.
- **Amplitude measurements** for each antenna, along with the total amplitude sum of all four antennas, updated at 5.87 MHz.
- **Beam position coordinates** (horizontal and vertical) updated at 5.87 MHz.
- **Phase information**, including the phase of each antenna signal and the phase of the summed signal relative to the phase reference line.

- **Phase reference line parameters**, including amplitude, phase, and raw signal data.

Averaged data within a user-defined Region of Interest (ROI), synchronized with selected timing events. These include the SUM amplitude, phase, and beam position, all processed within the FPGA firmware.

Figure 4: BPM RF radio receiver block diagram

The BPM radio receiver depicted in Figure 4 system consists of the following blocks:

- 1) BPM sensor: Signal source.
- 2) RF Front-End electronics: RF processing for achieving the Noise Figure, Dynamic range, stability and bandwidth required.
- 3) Analog down conversion: Converting the RF signals to a lower frequency for digitalization and for phase resolution improvements.
- 4) High speed digitalization and FPGA processing: Analog to digital conversion and digital signal processing.

Figure 5: BPM system block Diagram

Figure 5 depicts the generic layout of the BPM system.

- The analogue RF processing unit is responsible for filtering the undesirable harmonic components, satisfy the dynamic range by providing gain and attenuation to the RF signals and for calibrating the RF channels relative to the phase reference line signals. A trigger interface from the FPGA to the calibration RF switches is also available for synchronization purposes.
- The analogue downconversion stage is responsible for controlling the signal amplitude and converting the high frequency signals to the IF.
- The AMC digitizer has high speed digitizers (50 – 125 MSps) interfacing with an FPGA. A CPU connects to the FPGA via PCIe links.
- The timing receiver interfaces with the FPGA via the MicroTCA.4 backplane.

The BPM signals are transmitted through cables from the sensor to the electronics and are bundled together along its extension with the reference RF cables. The receiver channels are digitized separately, and phase and amplitudes are measured independently in the digital domain. Comparison of the digitized phase and amplitudes are performed in the FPGA firmware to provide the user with beam X and Y positions and relative phases between BPM sensor inputs and the reference signal. Near-IQ is used on the BPM receiver with an intermediate frequency to sample clock ratio of 4/15 providing a bandwidth of approximately 11.7MHz around the Intermediate Frequency (IF) without having nonlinear higher order frequency components lying within the first Nyquist zone of the digitized signal[15].

Every pair of BPM sensors are digitized in the same digitizer board as shown in the figure, allowing strong noise correlation between channels and improved relative thermal drifts between pairs of BPM's. The ESS BPM system measures the phase of each individual BPM, however for each pair of BPM sensors, this phase difference is measured in a single FPGA and can be used for low latency fast interlocks in future expansions of the system. The general scheme of how different BPM sensors are connected to the same MicroTCA.4 crate is shown in Figure 5.

A high bandwidth BPM system is also available in the MEBT, which is dedicated for high bandwidth measurements. It measures the signal of the top stripline of a pair of BPMs in the MEBT for performing absolute beam energy measurements. Raw data is produced from the system during 3 ms of data and at a sampling rate of 6.4 GSPs and 3 GHz bandwidth. The system is generally used for absolute time-of-flight measurements and bunching structure characterization as well as timing alignment of the LEBT and MEBT Choppers.

2.2.3 Beam Loss Monitors

The Beam Loss Monitoring (BLM) system provides information on the beam loss levels at each sensor location. Additionally, it is the main diagnostic system used for machine protection purposes in the SC parts of the linac. Two types of BLM systems differing in detector technology have been conceived at ESS. The neutron sensitive BLM (nBLM) system is based on 82 neutron detectors and primarily covers the lower energy part of the ESS linac[16][17]. Conversely, the Ionisation Chamber-based BLM (ICBLM) system consists of 266 ionisation chambers located almost exclusively throughout the SC parts of the linac[18].

2.2.3.1 nBLM

The nBLM system reports the number of detected neutrons per μs at the location of each detector. This information is derived from a 250 MSample/s data stream followed by signal corrections for pedestal and gain, and then neutron discrimination algorithms, all performed within an FPGA.

2.2.3.2 ICBLM

Within each ionization chamber, a continuous current is induced by the secondary particles traversing the chamber. These signals are sampled at 1 MSample/s and then an FPGA applies background subtraction to produce a result more correlated with the beam loss near each detector.

2.2.4 Faraday Cups

Faraday Cups (FC) and Insertable Beam Stops (IBS) were designed for the NCL and SCL, respectively. Both the FC and IBS are beam-interceptive devices, movable in or out of the beam line by means of a pneumatic actuator, and water cooled. These devices were designed for the specific energy range and the commissioning beam modes of the linac. Figure 6 illustrates the layout of a typical instance.

Figure 6: Block diagram of the Faraday Cup system

During the four commissioning phases of the ESS NCL between 2018 and 2023 [1-5], five different Faraday cups were used in place of expensive and bulky beam dumps in order to dump the beam at the end of each linac section under commissioning, and to measure the current of the proton beam in real-time[19][20][21][22][23]. The proton current was measured in the [0.1, 62.5] mA range, with an accuracy better than 1% and a time resolution better than 1 μ s. As an example, a measurement series captured during an ion source study is plotted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Current measurements from the Faraday Cup after the ESS ion source

3 Data Workflow

3.1 OVERVIEW

To provide input for the ML study, data was acquired during the commissioning of the NCL, with the most suitable data coming from the commissioning to the DTL4 FC at 74 MeV, particularly during stability runs. The acquisition configuration was straightforward, with a timing system sending a pattern of events for each pulse at a rate of 14 Hz, while beam diagnostics acquisition events marked the beam typically at 1 Hz or sometimes 14 Hz. PVs updated with each diagnostics event, promptly sending data over a 1 Gbps Ethernet connection to all clients. The primary data storage facility was the Archiver Appliance[24], and as discussed in Section 3.3, the initial deployment provided limited query and curation tools. The Task 10.6 team dedicated significant effort to data management, including extraction, transformation, cleaning, and other preparatory tasks, becoming key stakeholders of the data systems due to heavy use of the archived data. This work is described in Section 5, and the large fraction of effort that must be devoted to it is consistent with the experience of other teams applying ML to accelerators[25][26].

Lessons learned from Task 10.6 guided the development of new tools and data workflows for the upcoming commissioning of the entire linac and future ML applications. Upgrades to the archiver and SDS components will support large-scale data acquisition and exploitation, with an emphasis on ML and AI applications. These developments will benefit follow-on work beginning in Spring 2025, with the commissioning of the entire superconducting linac. The newly developed tools will be available not only to ESS but also to the wider EPICS community, enhancing efficiency and capabilities across the board.

3.2 DATA ACQUISITION COMPONENTS

In the data workflow, each instrumentation system acts as the data source incorporating the EPICS software toolkit, the MicroTCA platform and the global timing system to synchronize acquisition. The following sections describe these components in more detail.

3.2.1 EPICS

The control system for the entire ESS accelerator complex is built on EPICS, a widely adopted toolkit for distributed control systems. EPICS facilitates communication between monitoring and control operations over the network, enabling interaction with the underlying hardware via Input/Output Controllers (IOCs). It defines the network protocol, operational model, and client interfaces required for seamless control and data acquisition.

ESS is the first facility to fully utilize EPICS version 7, which introduces support for custom data structures, significantly enhancing flexibility in data handling and integration.

3.2.2 MicroTCA Systems

ESS has adopted MTCA technology as the standardized hardware platform for high-speed data acquisition. MTCA provides a modular and scalable architecture for integrating a high-performance

control system controller while it standardizes various external services interfaces, with the timing and synchronization system serving as a key example.

The MTCA platform interconnects high-speed digitizer cards (typically FPGA-based) with other critical components, such as timing modules and CPU systems, via a high-performance backplane infrastructure. This architecture enables:

- PCIe-based communication between FPGAs and CPUs, ensuring low-latency data transfer
- Clock and trigger distribution for precise synchronization
- Chassis management and control, enhancing system reliability and diagnostics

MTCA's deterministic synchronization capabilities and flexibility allow it to support diverse subsystems, including Low-Level RF (LLRF) as well as beam instrumentation applications. Of particular importance to Task 10.6, all relevant beam instrumentation systems utilize FPGA modules that support the low-latency link described in Section 4. Using this link, the instrumentation systems can source data with about μs latency for use by ML functions.

3.2.3 Timing System

The Timing System at ESS plays a crucial role in distributing synchronous triggers across different nodes, independent of their geographic location. Additionally, it ensures the precise distribution of the RF reference clock with minimal jitter, which is essential for maintaining synchronization across the entire accelerator.

The ESS timing system is implemented using Micro Research Finland (MRF) technology, built on MTCA hardware, and utilizing optical communication to link distributed nodes. This setup guarantees low-latency and high-precision timing, thus ensuring that all data acquisition and control processes remain synchronized with the accelerator's operational cycle.

3.3 THE ARCHIVER APPLIANCE: EXPERIENCE AND IMPROVEMENTS

The EPICS Archiver Appliance[24] is an application developed at SLAC, BNL and MSU for archiving data from the EPICS Control System. Its original scope was mostly around Scalar data, i.e. a temperature sensor updating at around 1 Hz. ESS did a study [27] on the performance characteristics for the originally planned usage of ~ 1 million PVs being archived and 10000 waveforms up to 10000 points being archived. The EPICS Archiver Appliance currently stores data in the binary protobuf format that was developed by Google[28].

At ESS the scope increased dramatically, we are currently archiving 901000 Scalar PVs producing around 423 GB per day and around 10000 waveforms from 20000 to 700000 points in size producing 1.3 TB a day.

3.3.1 Retrieval

The py-epicsarchiver module[29] is the main python client for retrieving data from the Archiver Appliance used at ESS. Initially the client used the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) interface for interacting with the archiver which converts the protobuf data in the archiver to the easy-to-understand JSON format. The JSON format has the advantage that it is human readable and so small

amounts of data can be quickly analysed by the eye, however that comes at a cost of size and CPU time in encoding.

For example, for 1 month of data of a double archived at 14Hz:

	JSON	Protobuf
Uncompressed size	2.22 GB	1.01GB
Time to send	59s	49s
Time to encode	359ms	9ms

This has another effect in that when using the JSON interface, the Archiver Appliance currently generates the whole JSON object in memory before delivering over the network. The JSON object is larger than the memory of the server hosting the archiver appliance it will hang. Considering some of the larger waveforms, even a week's worth of data can cause problems.

Hence, partly due to this project and other considerations the py-epicsarchiver was developed to use the protobuf interface instead of the JSON interface and gain access to the faster decoding and encoding. Another change was made to the EPICS Archiver Appliance to enable simple gzip compression on data sent between the Archiver and its clients:

	JSON	Protobuf
Compressed size	205MB	322MB

3.3.2 Storage of data

Some problems with using protobuf formatted files in the Archiver have emerged:

- The protobuf format requires any client to use a protobuf definition file and generate code for their application ahead of time.
- The protobuf format is not compressed at all in storage. Only file system compression is used.

In the large data format community Apache Parquet[30] has become a standard for storing large data due to its substantial set of features and high support in multiple programming languages. Two features are particularly useful for use in the Archiver Appliance:

- Multiple options of Compression per data column
- Schema is stored in the file

Hence, we have started a project to integrate Parquet files as an alternative to the current protobuf format in the Archiver Appliance.

With a prototype implementation we have:

	Protobuf	Parquet
Waveform 100 elements 0.25Hz	2.3GB	400MB
Double at 14Hz	4.5GB	1.1GB

3.3.3 Data Ingestion

Another problem is that when a PV updates, it will always send new data to the Archiver Appliance, whether that event will be archived or not. In this case the EPICS control system could be saturating the network interface of the device before it even arrives at the Archiver.

To solve this, we have implemented EPICS filters into the capabilities of the Archiver Appliance. This means you can specify a filter on the data produced by the PV before it even reaches the Archiver, both reducing the load on the Archiver and on the machine that is producing the data.

3.4 SYNCHRONOUS DATA SERVICE: IN DEVELOPMENT FOR SCALABLE ACQUISITION OF NOMINAL AND ANOMALOUS PULSE DATA

3.4.1 Introduction

The ESS accelerator complex consists of multiple instrumentation and other subsystems, all of which generate vast amounts of data crucial for machine operation, troubleshooting, and analysis. The scale of data production is significant: the radio frequency (RF) systems alone number in the hundreds, while instrumentation sensors—including beam position monitors (BPMs), beam current monitors (BCMs), and beam loss monitors (BLMs)—number over 500. These high-performance systems digitize analogue signals at rates reaching hundreds of megahertz.

To ensure a scalable, consistent, and high-performance approach to collecting, storing, and analysing high-resolution data from these instruments, ESS is developing the Synchronous Data Service (SDS)[31]. SDS is designed to integrate seamlessly with the ESS control system, providing a structured framework for synchronous data acquisition and retrieval.

3.4.2 Synchronous Data Service (SDS) Architecture

Given that ESS operates as a pulsed machine, its timing scheme divides time into discrete cycles synchronized with the machine’s maximum repetition rate, which at ESS is 14 Hz. Each 14 Hz cycle is assigned a unique cycle ID, which serves as an indexing mechanism for machine control system data. This cycle-based indexing provides a more systematic and efficient way to correlate data across different subsystems, enhancing the traditional timestamp-based approach.

During each cycle, the timing master distributes information to timing receivers, including key operational parameters such as:

- Beam current
- Beam destination
- Beam mode

- Machine status

This metadata is retrieved at the EPICS IOCs at the device level, allowing measurement data to be packaged together with operational metadata early in the data acquisition chain. By embedding this metadata directly into the measurement process, SDS ensures consistent and structured data correlation across multiple subsystems. A simple overview of the SDS dataflow architecture can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Overview of SDS dataflow

3.4.3 Integration with EPICS and Custom Data Structures

In traditional EPICS implementations, standard data types include fields for value, alarms, and timestamps. However, EPICS does not inherently support structured data types—this capability must be explicitly enabled through IOC configuration modifications.

The SDS software framework provides a dedicated EPICS module that defines a custom data structure, compliant with EPICS Normative Types (NT) conventions. This structure enables the packaging of measurement values together with metadata, including the cycle ID, which serves as a fundamental reference for synchronizing data across multiple instruments.

At the IOC level, the goal is to expose measurement data as an EPICS PV, augmented with a special metadata field containing the cycle ID. This approach allows measurements from the same cycle to be easily correlated across different subsystems, facilitating advanced data analysis, diagnostics, and machine learning applications.

3.4.4 SDS Collector Service

The second major component of the SDS software architecture is the collector service, which is responsible for:

1. Monitoring SDS-enhanced PVs on the EPICS network
2. Retrieving and processing measurement data in real time
3. Indexing and storing data by cycle ID for permanent archival and future analysis

By integrating structured data acquisition at the IOC level and providing a dedicated collector service for efficient storage and retrieval, SDS establishes a scalable and synchronized data framework for ESS operations. This enables precise event correlation across multiple subsystems, significantly improving machine diagnostics, performance analysis, and potential machine learning applications. An overview of the current architecture of the SDS Collector is depicted in Figure 9:

Figure 9: Overview of the SDS Collector system

3.4.5 Post-Mortem and Data-on-Demand Capabilities

The raw and processed analogue data acquired by the MTCA-based acquisition systems in the ESS accelerator complex is highly valuable for operational monitoring, diagnostics, and post-mortem analysis. To ensure a standardized and consistent approach to data archiving, ESS has adopted a centralized storage solution rather than relying on local storage at individual IOC hosts. Local storage would require additional retrieval processes across multiple hosts, introducing inefficiencies and potential data fragmentation.

However, transmitting large datasets over the network in real time is impractical due to bandwidth constraints, even with gigabit Ethernet interfaces. Indiscriminately streaming high-resolution data would risk overloading the network and impacting real-time accelerator operations.

3.4.5.1 Efficient Data Management with Local Circular Buffers

To address this challenge, the ESS SDS module for EPICS IOCs implements a local circular buffer mechanism for SDS Process Variables (PVs). This buffer stores a configurable number of data frames locally, ensuring that measurement values remain available for retrieval without immediate network transmission.

Key characteristics of this buffering approach are:

- Data is not published to the network until explicitly requested

- Buffered values are transmitted gradually, with a controlled delay between updates
- Network load is distributed over time, preventing congestion, and ensuring stable IOC performance

This approach optimizes network usage while preserving access to high-resolution data for post-mortem and on-demand retrieval.

3.4.5.2 Post-Mortem Data Retrieval

SDS enables post-mortem data collection by reacting to the post-mortem event broadcast on the timing network. When a post-mortem event occurs, SDS:

- Retrieves the latest datasets acquired just before and after the event
- Uploads the buffered data to central storage, ensuring it is available for detailed analysis
- Minimizes disruption by efficiently managing network bandwidth during the upload process

This mechanism ensures that critical data surrounding faults, beam trips, or anomalies is readily available for diagnostics and machine protection analysis.

3.4.5.3 Data-on-Demand Mechanism

Beyond post-mortem retrieval, the same buffering strategy enables a general-purpose data-on-demand collection system. This is triggered by a dedicated timing network event, named "data-on-demand", which allows for flexible data acquisition based on specific operational conditions.

Possible use cases for data-on-demand include:

- Triggered data collection following an interesting machine condition. As a result of the Task 10.6 work, a trained ML model could classify this condition and assert the DoD trigger.
- Threshold-based data acquisition, where data is retrieved if a parameter exceeds a predefined limit
- Periodic monitoring, allowing steady-state data collection at scheduled intervals for trend analysis and long-term system health assessment. For ML models that require training data, this periodic monitoring will be configured to provide substantial data sets without straining control system resources.

3.4.6 Current Status

The Synchronous Data Service (SDS) project is still in its early development stage. The first release of the EPICS SDS module was completed in October 2024 and has been deployed across all 91 Low-Level RF (LLRF) and RF Local Protection MTCA systems currently operational at ESS.

As part of the initial scalability testing, we have begun using data-on-demand requests to facilitate the upload of local buffers. The next phase of deployment will extend SDS integration to Beam Instrumentation systems, with a primary focus on Beam Position Monitors (BPMs) and Beam Current Monitors (BCMs).

At this stage, the SDS ecosystem of tools is still under development. Currently:

- Configuration is performed manually, requiring users to predefine the SDS PVs of interest

- The SDS Collector monitors a specified list of PV names, retrieves data after a collection event, and saves the results into a single Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5) file
- These files are stored on a dedicated storage server, which is automatically mounted within JupyterHub instances—a Python-based notebook environment widely used at ESS for data manipulation and analysis

3.4.7 Future Plans

Since all SDS software components are still in an early stage, further development cycles will be required to bring the system to production-grade quality.

Planned optimizations include:

- Reducing latencies in the SDS IOC module, particularly in the correlation process between dataset timestamps and cycle ID metadata from the timing system
- Enhancing SDS Collector performance, as large-scale testing will help identify necessary improvements to support full-scale data ingestion across all ESS instruments

Beyond system optimizations, the development of an SDS tool ecosystem is a key priority. Several functionalities need to be implemented:

1. Data Cataloguing & Organization: Efficient methods for indexing and managing collected data files
2. Query & Retrieval Tools: User-friendly tools for accessing stored data efficiently
3. Integration with the EPICS Archiver: Combining traditional time-series EPICS PV data with SDS records to provide a seamless data retrieval experience
4. Advanced Data Analysis Frameworks: Leveraging cluster computing for parallel processing of large datasets

Initial discussions have explored using Dask, a Python-based parallel computing framework, as a foundation for large-scale data analysis. However, a final decision on the computational framework is still pending.

3.4.7.1 SDS in the context of Machine Learning

The Synchronous Data Service (SDS) establishes a high-resolution, time-correlated data acquisition framework, essential for advanced data analysis and machine learning applications in accelerator diagnostics, anomaly detection and optimization. By leveraging custom structured data types provided by EPICS 7, SDS enables seamless integration of complex, multi-dimensional datasets that preserve critical metadata, such as cycle synchronization and operational parameters. This structured approach ensures that machine learning models can access rich, well-organized datasets with minimal preprocessing, facilitating more effective training and inference. As SDS evolves and its ecosystem of tools expands, it will provide an improving foundation for applying AI-driven techniques to improve accelerator performance, reliability, and overall operational efficiency.

3.5 STRATEGY FOR THE FUTURE: ESS FRAMEWORK FOR OPERATIONS DATA

Motivated by the experience of Task 10.6 as well as by other data-intensive studies, ESS has developed a broader strategy for data management called the ESS Framework for Operation Data. The tools described in Sections 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4 are the first components of this framework and the I.FAST team has been actively engaged in their development and deployment as part of Task 10.6. Due to its importance for current and future ML/AI applications, the full framework is presented in this section.

3.5.1 Framework Description

The operation of ESS systems - including the linac, target, and neutron scattering systems - will produce a diverse range of data. This spans from sporadically modified configuration data to scalar data with varying update rates, as well as high-frequency multidimensional data, such as from SDS/DoD. Analysing the collected data will provide crucial information for the commissioning, operation, tuning and maintenance, ultimately optimising the performance of the neutron instruments.

The “ESS Framework for ESS Operations Data” encompasses the entirety of tools and mechanisms at ESS which enable the collection, storage, and analysis of operations data in a cooperatively managed and developed framework. The framework establishes the data governance mandates and workflows, such as prioritizing data based on shared resources and capacity constraints.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of the framework for ESS Operations Data and interactions with different systems and users.

The framework serves a broad range of users across the organization, including operations teams as well as engineering and physics experts, as shown in Figure 10. Framework level descriptions are typically technology-agnostic, focusing on the purpose and context of the technical design and implementation without prescribing specific technologies (software or hardware).

Figure 11: Schematic of the data framework

A simplified diagram of the framework architecture is presented in Figure 11. *Data producers*, such as proton beam diagnostic systems, generate operations data. This may include beam diagnostics signals, or local AI kernel output data, or interpreted results from a concentrator function like differential beam current measurements. Selected operations data is collected and stored in the *federated storage*, which is composed of various specialised storage services. Data users will access this data using the *data access and analysis portal*, which provides powerful query services to locate the data of interest, run data reduction and correlation algorithms, visualise the data, and retrieve the data for further offline processing in suitable formats. For complex tasks requiring multiple steps and intermediate results, task-specific datasets shall be supported. These are subsets of operations data, selected and copied into a logically separated space, where data analysts can manipulate and store the dataset as needed. This setup also supports the preparation for ML training data, using actual ESS operations data. The framework-wide governance is expected to streamline the process from initial data production to end-user provision.

Figure 12 shows an internal block diagram of the technical architecture of the framework for ESS Operations Data. Data flows from producers (left) to the data collection and storage systems, which may include EPICS Archiver, SDS collector, Alarms, or others. Aggregation functions then deliver the data to the applications within the Data access and analysis portal – such as future ML training support functions, or analysis functions studying ML algorithms in actual operation.

Figure 12: Internal block diagram of the framework for ESS Operations Data. Lines from the data producers indicate how runtime data reaches the data access and analysis portal via the aggregation functions, i.e. either as is (dashed lines) or after passing through the federated storage (solid lines). Dotted, double-pointed arrows indicate monitoring and curating functions applied to different services on the framework level.

3.5.2 Role of the framework for Machine Learning in practice

The ESS Framework for Operations Data supports ML applications in the following key areas:

- **Generation of ML training data.** The framework provides a technical and governance structure for collecting, preparing and delivering training data. Training data sets can be used for improving ML models in ESS use, or for investigations comparing the performance (prediction power, execution time) of various ML algorithms. By enforcing a policy of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data[32], the framework will enable collaborative ML developments across and beyond ESS.
- **Analysis of ML effectiveness.** The framework includes functions for studying the ML behaviour in ESS operation, thus enabling the verification and validation of ML functions. Low latency behaviour analysis is expected to benefit particularly from the SDS/DoD data collection. For applications like “Intelligent Triggers”, where ML models may trigger DoD capture of interesting anomalies, the framework supports detailed studies of cause-and-effect relationships.

3.5.3 Current status

As of Q1 2025, the ESS Framework for Operations Data is partially implemented. Most data producers are in place, but further integration with the federated storage is required. Many aspired functions for the Data access and analysis portal need more requirements analysis and design work. The framework’s governance functions are identified and require stepwise organizational implementation and refinement in the upcoming ESS commissioning periods.

4 Low Latency Platform

4.1 ARCHITECTURE

4.1.1 Introduction

The significant component of this task has been to investigate the options of running a protection ML algorithm on data from a wide array of acquisition systems with such low latency that it could stop the machine during the machine cycle. This means receiving and applying an ML algorithm on data from hundreds of detectors and reacting with sub millisecond latency. The end goal would be that the system could be connected to the Fast Beam Interlock System (FBIS) and stop the machine if damaging conditions are identified.

To be able to achieve these latencies, a number of requirements can be extracted:

- The data needs to be transferred from all of the acquisition systems with predictability and with as low latency as possible. This means that data should not be lost because of congestion or data subjected to long delays. This rules out using the normal data network for low-latency transmissions.
- The system receiving the data needs to be able to apply the ML model on incoming data on the fly. This would rule out storing the data on a server and evaluating it CPU/GPU solution. Instead, the use-case is closer to an edge application where FPGAs have been used to for instance evaluate images on the fly without SW in the loop.

4.1.2 Overview

Based on the requirements a prototype architecture was proposed that would cover normal conducting section (NCL) of the linear accelerator. This prototype has been described in more detail in the MS48 report [0]. The overview of the prototype is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: FPGA ML system overview. Lower layer: The schematic of the ESS linac. Middle layer: The beam instrumentation acquisition systems that are providing the initial data sets, and the Machine Learning FPGA platform that is being prototyped. Top layer: Software tools and persistent data store

The top-layer shown in Figure 13 is the normal data workflow described in chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**. The middle layer shows the acquisition systems located in the gallery. Since all systems have Small Form-factor (SFP) transceivers, these can be used to connect the systems together in a data network with optical-fibres in its own data transmission network. This work has been broken out to its own project called the Minimum-latency Optical Data Acquisition Link (MODAL), described in 4.2. Further investigations of data transmissions and protocols is explored in that section. The final part is the selection of the main FPGA system that runs the ML model. The down selection and different methodologies are described in section 4.1.4.

The plan is then to expand the prototype to cover the entire LINAC. The summary of the systems is in **Error! Reference source not found.**. For the time being, the camera systems are not included. The bandwidth numbers are the maximum estimated, note that the total differs since not all cards are connected to the same number of detectors. The prototype system amount of acquisitions systems and FPGA cards are within parenthesis.

Table 1: FPGA ML systems summary and bandwidths

System	Acquisitions systems	FPGA cards	Bandwidth (max per card)	Bandwidth (total)
<i>BPM</i>	18 (3)	49 (10)	193 MB/s	9457 MB/s
<i>BCM</i>	9 (1)	9 (1)	1232 MB/s	5104 MB/s
<i>FC</i>	1 (1)	1 (1)	88 MB/s	88 MB/s
<i>nBLM</i>	10 (2)	16 (6)	240 MB/s	3840 MB/s
<i>icBLM</i>	17 (2)	37 (2)	32 MB/s	1184 MB/s
<i>APTM</i>	4	8	32 MB/s	256 MB/s
<i>GRID</i>	1	10	32 MB/s	320 MB/s

Further details on what type of data is being transmitted is covered in the next section.

4.1.3 Acquisition system data

The systems themselves and the data they produce were introduced in section 2.2. In contrast, this section focuses on how this data is transmitted on the optical links. There are still certain open questions around the difference between the data collected and the data transmitted across FPGAs, as the collected data is usually converted to human-readable format (Amperes, Voltage etc.), while the lower-level data is unformatted. Note that the systems described are the main ones that have been used in the ML analyses or are expected to be added to the effort next.

4.1.3.1 Beam Current Monitor (BCM)

The FPGA systems transmit this in its raw form as a 16-bit signed integer which is captured at 88 MSample/s. The window around the pulse is typically a bit more than the configured pulse length, so slightly more than 3 ms. When there is no beam, the signal should be settling around zero, and this signal between pulses is also available.

The BCM system is connected to up to 8 sensors which implies rather high raw data bandwidth. There may be a need to decimate this waveform for bandwidth purposes.

4.1.3.2 Beam Position Monitor (BPM)

The X, Y and Phase waveforms are all downsampled by 15 from the 88 MSample/s base frequency, so each waveform is about 5.8 MSample/s.

The X/Y positions in raw form are 16-bit signed integers and can be interpreted as a percentage value on how far off-centre the beam is. It is typically multiplied with a sensor-specific factor to convert it to microns.

The raw phase value is harder to interpret as it is a fixed-point format with 3 integer bits and 12 fractional bits and together it represents the phase in radians from π to $-\pi$. This presents a challenge since our presented data is usually converted into degrees.

4.1.3.3 Neutron sensitive Beam Loss Monitor (nBLM)

The neutron count is summarised for each 1 μ s window, hence, the raw data from an nBLM detector is a 32-bit unsigned integer at 1 MSample/s.

It is worth noting that like the BCM, the BLM systems are running continuously and data outside of the normal beam window might be interesting.

4.1.3.4 Ionisation Chamber-based BLM (ICBLM)

The Ionization Chambers are connected to a transimpedance readout which measures the current in nA to mA ranges and is directly connected to an FPGA. To remove RF-induced photon signals, this background is measured and subtracted from the input signal.

The background corrected waveforms are currently the candidate for input data to the ML model. They are measured at 1 MSample/s and have 20-bits of precision, which is usually padded to a signed 32-bit integer.

4.1.4 Main FPGA platform evaluation

One of the main things to consider when it comes to the evaluation of the ML model is how easy it is to apply to embedded technology. There are a couple of different technologies to consider.

ML models built directly out of FPGA logic like hls4ml [36]. The benefit is that these models can run very fast, and are very suitable for streaming data. The major downside is that there is a complex procedure to get the model adapted and a re-trained model needs to redo at least part of the process. It also requires the expertise of someone with FPGA knowledge.

The more attractive offerings are the ML frameworks that the two major FPGA vendors are working on. As ESS is using a single vendor, we have been only looking at the AMD offering during this project.

Figure 14 AMD Tool flow for Machine learning on Zynq or Versal type FPGAs.

Figure 14 shows the AMD (previously Xilinx) methodology where the goal is to simplify and enable a simpler environment for data scientists working with the training of models to deploy them onto hardware. The HW/SW developer can provide the environment for any hardware specific implementations, like in our case, we want to be able to evaluate the model on incoming data from all of the systems buffered in the programmable FPGA logic.

The actual processing of the ML model is done on specific accelerator elements in the FPGA. In the case of the Zynq, this is AMD Deep Learning Processor cores (DPU) made in FPGA logic. For Versal there are already specific DPU cores for ML built into the chip for this purpose.

This gives a lot of flexibility when it comes to trying different models or even running multiple models at the same time.

There are more details in the investigations performed in the MS48 report [0]. But the preferred choice for the main FPGA is Versal AI based board, it has several advantages:

- It has a large number of hardware AI cores that run at much higher frequencies than the DPU cores made for programmable logic. There are also programming models for taking data directly from the programmable logic which means we should be able to run an ML algorithm without having to store the data off-chip in memory.
- The DPU cores for programmable logic take up significant space and what configuration to use depends on the model performance. The DPU tests where only run on memory-to-memory

image jobs, so is more like the flow with a model run on an incoming camera image stored in memory.

- Overall, the DPU performance isn't great. It can run with significantly lower latency than a GPU solution, as it can run in a tight SW loop directly on the incoming data. But it does require SW in the loop, the SW also needs to be adapted based on the DPU configuration.
- As a final note that using a Versal core does not exclude the option of running a pure FPGA based ML model made with hls4ml for instance.

Deploying an ML model on Versal hardware is discussed further in section 6.

4.2 MINIMUM-LATENCY OPTICAL DATA ACQUISITION LINK

4.2.1 Introduction

Based on the work described in the previous section, the IFAST Task 10.6 team proposed a collaboration with the Warsaw Technical University (WUT) to realize the low latency platform at the scale of the entire ESS accelerator facility. With the Polish Ministry of Science providing significant support, work on the Minimum-Latency Optical Data Acquisition Link (MODAL) commenced and is described in this separate section. It is critically relevant for Task 10.6 because it builds on the Task 10.6 platform work and also because it will host the results of the Task 10.6 ML algorithm work.

4.2.2 Motivation

As explained in 4.1.2, diagnostic systems collectively generate well over 100 Gbps of data. The data is processed independently, with only a tiny fraction analysed together. Converging all diagnostic data in a centralized location could provide substantial benefits for accelerator diagnostics. Centralized analysis would allow a more complete look at the accelerator behaviour and support ML models that could allow earlier detection of potential problems and failures.

The existing ethernet-based communication infrastructure is insufficient for managing all systems' data collection. A new system was needed to allow for high-speed communication and fast data processing. This system should offer low signal latency and doesn't require any major hardware modifications.

Various transmission media were evaluated for their suitability in this system. Optical fibres were identified as a leading option due to their capability for high-speed data transfer and the availability of existing infrastructure at ESS. Light propagates through optical fibres at approximately 200,000 kilometres per second, about 67% of the speed of light in a vacuum. The optical fibres can be easily interfaced by using SFP or QSFP modules (Fig. 1). The optical fibre network is already available at ESS, making integrating the system easier.

Figure 15: Photo of QSFP and SFP+ transceivers

Coaxial RF cables were also considered as a potential transmission medium. Signals propagate through RF coaxial cables at approximately 66% to 85% of the speed of light in a vacuum, depending on the cable's dielectric material. The coaxial cables can support low-latency applications such as the discussed system. However, they are expensive and may require specialized transmitters. This will result in much more complex integration into the current ESS infrastructure.

Twisted pair cables were a third option that was considered. Twisted pair cables are relatively cheap. The velocity factor for Cat 7 twisted pair cables is at the level between 74 - 79%, depending on the cable model. The twisted pair cables should offer the lowest propagation delay. However, their performance is limited in terms of transmission speed. Achieving speeds of up to 10 Gbps is possible over distances of up to 10 meters, but this necessitates using significantly more transceivers. Consequently, twisted pair cables are more suitable for short, low-throughput connections than high-speed, long-distance ones.

After this analysis, optical fibres were selected as the most suitable transmission medium. While optical fibres have a slightly slower propagation speed (67% of the speed of light in a vacuum) compared to some coaxial RF and twisted pair cables, their higher bandwidth and ease of integration were the deciding factors.

4.2.3 FPGA and Multigigabit transceivers

All relevant beam diagnostic systems utilize FPGAs equipped with multi-gigabit transceivers. They can be used for high-speed data transmission and the data transfer protocols can be optimized to minimize latency.

To achieve efficient data aggregation and transfer, a dedicated system for collecting data from diagnostic systems is required. Although various FPGAs with differing numbers of transceivers are available on the market, no single chip can directly collect the data from all systems. This limitation necessitates the creation of a networked system in which multiple modules work together to collect and forward data to a central processing unit. Several FPGA platforms were evaluated to determine their suitability for the system:

Zynq Ultrascale: Equipped with up to 24 transceivers and includes an integrated processor,

Virtex Ultrascale: Equipped with up to 96 transceivers,

Kintex Ultrascale: Equipped with up to 32 transceivers

Versal: Equipped with up to 44 transceivers, this family offers additional AI cores making this platform suitable for high-performance computing.

The design of this network must be flexible and scalable to ensure the possibility of future extensions. Each diagnostic system must be able to transmit data to the central processing unit. The data can be passed through several concentrators utilizing SFP transceivers and optical fibres. The concentrators will pass the data to the central unit.

Another crucial aspect of the system is optimizing the data transfer protocols utilized by the transceivers and selection of the central unit FPGA chip. The Versal platform was selected due to a large number of multigigabit transceivers and advanced signal processing capability. To minimize the design cost and time off the shelf, the AMD Versal VCK190 module, shown in Fig. 2, was selected.

Figure 16: Photo of the AMD Versal VCK190

Due to a limited number of transceivers, the board cannot gather data from all systems. Therefore, a set of concentrators is needed. It was decided that it would be best to use Zynq Ultrascale+ SoCs. They offer a reasonable number of fast transceivers, and the integrated CPU will make system control easier.

A simplified architecture of the system is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Simplified block diagram of the proposed system

4.2.4 Transmission protocol

The transmission between diagnostic systems, concentrators and processing unit shall be realized using packet transmission. Such an approach allows the mixing of data from different systems into a single stream. With the right packet header, the data source and timing can be decoded.

The main drawback of the packet transmission is the addition of header data that will limit the effective transmission speed. The impact of the header data can be adjusted by changing the size of the packet. Larger packets improve transmission speed but may result in increased system latency. Smaller packets reduce latency at the expense of transmission speed. Different packet sizes can be used to optimize the performance during the system operation.

The basic principle of the packet transmission operation is presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18: The block diagram illustrating the principle of the packet concentrator.

4.2.5 Expected performance

The performance of the system is mostly limited by the number and speed of multigigabit transceivers used in central processing unit. 30 transceivers placed on the selected VCK190 module can be used. The transceivers can be operated with speeds up to 16 Gbps. This results in theoretical maximum transmission speed of 480 Gbps. However, in a practical implementation, the actual transmission speed will be lower due to several factors:

- **Error Correction Encoding:** To ensure error-free transmission, an encoding protocol must be employed. The choice of encoding impacts the transmission speed, with potential reductions ranging from 10% to 50%.
- **Packet Transmission Overhead:** The use of packet-based transmission introduces additional overhead, which is expected to reduce the effective speed by 5% to 10%.
- **Link Utilization:** In practice, the data links will not operate at full capacity. An effective utilization of approximately 80% of the link speed is anticipated.

Taking all this into account result in a worst-case scenario transmission speed of 172.8 Gbps, which is over 1.5 times the current requirement. With improved error correction techniques, transmission speeds exceeding 300 Gbps can be achieved.

4.2.6 Summary

The data from all beam instrumentation systems at ESS cannot be directly transmitted to the central unit. The proposed system uses a tree-like structure to transmit the data with the additional concentrators to gather the data into a single stream that can be passed to another concentrator or to the central processing unit. These intermediate nodes will serve as scalable components that support system extension, scalable to the entire ESS linac and applicable to similarly large accelerator facilities. The hardware is in construction and initial testing on the ESS site is scheduled for March 2025.

5 Analysis of ESS commissioning data

5.1 INTRODUCTION

To assess the predictive capabilities and limitations of an ML model used for supervised binary classification, a set of well-defined, labelled data is required. This is then used to train the algorithm to label the data as good or bad. For the applications of interest, the former represents normal operation, while the latter represents the off-normal operation that led to beam production suppression (for example, a beam trip or an interlock). The data used for the purpose of this project were collected during commissioning of the ESS NCL, where, contrary to steady operation, normal and off-normal data is still to be identified. With such data, a clustering study is required before an assessment of ML binary classifiers can be performed. This study aims to explore whether/how the data can be grouped into clusters, such that each cluster can be connected to either normal operation or certain types of beam trips. This section summarises the work performed on a clustering study with scalar and time-

series variables measured by the ESS beam instrumentation during NCL commissioning up to 74 MeV during the Summer of 2023. Several dedicated stability runs with limited machine commissioning activities have been performed, each lasting from 1h to 18h. The first part of this section focuses on work performed on one of the stability runs constituting one dataset, while the second part summarises the results from extension to several datasets over approximately two weeks of ESS commissioning data.

5.2 DATA CLUSTERING WITH ONE DATASET

Selected scalar and time-series data acquired by the BCM and the BPM systems per machine cycle during about 400 GB representing about 13 hours of these runs have been extracted from the Archiver Appliance (described in Section 3.3) for offline analysis on a local machine. As noted previously, several challenges limiting the rate of progress have been encountered during the process, mostly related to download speed, data format, and query performance.

As part of offline pre-processing step, the extracted BPM time-series data were first grouped into datasets. Grouping is based on the average current measured by the BCM (DTL4-BCM) located just before the beam destination (at end of DTL tank 4). Each dataset consisted of the data prior to a beam trip from consecutive machine cycles with measured average BCM beam current above a selected threshold. The optimal value for this threshold was found to be 1 mA, resulting in about 12000 machine cycles of data. Each time-series was then further trimmed to leave only the representative part of the waveform (3000 out of 110000 points), resulting in data ready for the classification study.

The first subsection summarises the work on clustering study where the same method is applied on individual BCM time-series data, while the second subsection focuses on expanding to clustering with two BPM and/or BCM time-series simultaneously.

5.2.1 Separate time-series clustering

To identify normal and off-normal time-series data, the K-shape clustering algorithm[33] has been applied to each time-series individually. This algorithm is a type of unsupervised ML, which groups a set of time-series examples into clusters based on their shape similarity. A particular feature of this algorithm is a similarity measure that ensures invariance to time shift and amplitude. The cluster count, k , is a required fixed input to the algorithm. In order to determine k , the Elbow Method was used, where the average similarity measure (within-cluster-sum-of-square, WCSS), S , is extracted for different cluster counts. Here S is calculated as the sum of the squares of similarity measures between examples in each cluster and cluster centroid. The optimal k value is then extracted as the point at which the graph of $S(k)$ forms an elbow. An example of an elbow plot is shown later in Figure 23.

Figure 19: Results of the K-shape algorithm applied to one of the BPM sum magnitude time-series (top, for DTL3 BPM2 SM) and one of the BCM current timeseries (bottom, DTL4 BCM) with optimal number of clusters found to be $k=4$ and $k=5$, respectively. Right: bar chart with number of timeseries examples in each cluster type. Upper: time evolution of DTL4-BCM beam current per cycle, (right Y axis scale) with marker colour indicating the identified cluster type as in the bar chart. Black curve indicates beam interlock status. Left: example timeseries for each cluster type, the colour indicates the identified cluster type. (FBIS_RBI_OK where 1 refers to "OK" and 0 to "not OK"). Middle: cluster centroid (coloured line, colour as defined in the bar chart) for each cluster.

This technique was applied to BPM phase and magnitude time-series data, where clustering was performed on each time-series individually. A distinct elbow point was observed in the magnitude data, with k values typically between 4 and 6, while the phase data graphs exhibit no clear elbow shape. In case of magnitude data, the results indicate certain degree of correlation with the average beam current per cycle measured by the DTL4-BCM - see Figure 19. No clear change in the time-series type prior to the beam trip was found for neither magnitude nor phase data.

5.2.2 Clustering of time-series pairs

Single time-series clustering does not show clear, distinct clusters present just before the beam interlocks. This indicates low correlation between the time-series shape and beam interlocks in the dataset under study. Another possibility that might be better suited to distinguish off-normal, problematic beam pulses leading to beam trips from the normal ones is to look at several signals simultaneously. Here, the idea is to explore the correlations between different systems and/or between different data within a specific system. For this project, simultaneous clustering of two BPM and/or BCM signals was explored. The pair combinations included in the study are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: List of time-series pairs used for multi-series clustering. Here SM and SA refer to BPM sum phase and magnitude (amplitude), respectively. The numbers after the system name represent the location of this system in a section running geographically from the ion source to beam destination, i.e., DTL4 BPM1 represents 1st BPM in the DTL tank 4.

2 BCM waveforms	
MEBT BCM2	DTL1 BCM1
MEBT BCM2	DTL4 BCM1
2 BPM waveforms, various combinations	
MEBT BPM3 SM	DTL1 BPM6 SM
MEBT BPM3 SA	DTL1 BPM6 SA
MEBT BPM3 SA	DTL1 BPM6 SM
MEBT BPM3 SM	DTL1 BPM6 SA
MEBT BPM3 SM	DTL4 BPM1 SM
MEBT BPM3 SA	DTL4 BPM1 SA
MEBT BPM3 SA	DTL4 BPM1 SM
MEBT BPM3 SM	DTL4 BPM1 SA

1 BCM and 1 BPM waveform	
DTL4 BCM	DTL4 BPM1 SM
DTL4 BCM	DTL4 BPM1 SA
MEBT BCM2	DTL4 BPM1 SM
MEBT BCM2	DTL4 BPM1 SA
DTL4 BCM	MEBT BPM3 SM
DTL4 BCM	MEBT BPM3 SA

In the following two sections, the procedure used for data preparation and clustering steps is explained and then the results of the analysis are presented.

5.2.2.1 Data preparation for clustering and clustering steps

Data preparation and clustering steps with time-series pairs are generally similar to the case of single time-series with exception of scaling applied to certain time-series in order to handle the large amplitude differences between the signals in each pair. In the following the procedure used for data preparation followed by clustering is explained for an example pair, namely, [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] and consists of:

- data trimming of each timeseries,
- combining and scaling of timeseries pairs,
- application of the clustering algorithm and cluster count determination.

Full BCM and BPM time-series contain 400000 and 100000 data points respectively. After data trimming is applied, each single time-series contains around 1000 data points. The trimming is necessary in order to reduce the amount of data being processed in clustering and thus significantly increase the processing speed. The points in the trimmed time-series are chosen to include points from before and after the time window of allowed beam pulse locations. See Figure 20 for original and trimmed time-series data in the case of example pair [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM].

After trimming, the two time-series from each machine cycle are combined into a single time-series. In case the beam pulse amplitudes in the combined time-series differ significantly, the time-series with the larger amplitude is scaled by dividing by a scaling factor specific to the time-series pair. The scaling factor selection was performed manually for each pair combination. For the case of [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM], scaling was required, and the scaling factor was chosen to be 120. An example of a combined time-series for this pair before and after scaling is shown in Figure 21. The

time-series constituting the whole dataset for this pair is shown in Figure 22. This set of time-series represents the final data ready for the clustering steps for the [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair.

Figure 20: Original (top) and trimmed (bottom) MEBT BCM2 (left) and DTL4 BPM1 SM (right) timeseries collected at machine cycle with start time stamp 2023-07-09 00:35:02.225600768+00:00. For the BCM data, the cut start and end point were set to 34730 and 35800, respectively. For the BPM data the cut start and end were chosen to be at points 2000 and 3000, respectively.

Figure 21: Combined unscaled (left) and scaled (right) time-series for the [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] at machine cycle 2023-07-09 00:35:02.225000+00:00.

Figure 22: Combined and scaled timeseries for [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair in the full dataset consisting of 5999 machine cycles. This set of timeseries represent the final data ready for the clustering steps in case the [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair.

Figure 23: Elbow graph extracted for the case of [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair with distinct elbow shape.

Like in the case of single time-series, the clustering was performed with the K-shape cluster algorithm. This algorithm requires a fixed cluster count (K value) as an input. As in the case of single time-series clustering, the Elbow method was used to determine the K value. The elbow graph shows the similarity measure S as a function of K value, where S again represents the within-the-cluster-sum-of-squares (WCSS) values. The optimal K value is then determined as the point at which the graph forms an elbow inflection. Figure 23 shows the elbow graph extracted for the case of [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM], where the optimal K value was found to be 10. For each K value, a dataset is passed to the K-shape algorithm for clustering. Each combined time-series is assigned to a certain cluster, and a centroid (average) combined time-series is calculated for each cluster.

Figure 24: Centroid (top) and individual (middle, black curves) combined timeseries for 10 clusters (optimal K value) in case of the [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair clustering. The colours in bar chart with number of combined timeseries in each cluster (bottom) represent the clusters and follow the same colour assignment in all plots in this figure.

Figure 24Figure 28 shows the centroids for $K=10$ and all individual combined timeseries in each cluster for the case of the [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair. Additionally, the bar chart with the combined time-series count in each cluster is also shown. The centroid and individual time-series plots demonstrate the K-shape method’s invariance to amplitude and phase shift.

To visually determine correlation between cluster types (related to timeseries shapes) and interlock events, as in Figure 19, the clustering results are plotted on the beam interlock (FBIS_RBI_OK) time evolution plot together with the average beam current data measured by the last BCM (DTL4 BCM) located just before the beam destination. Each BCM average current data point is plotted with its corresponding cluster colour. These results for the pair [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] are shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Time evolution of the interlock (black line, left Y scale) and average beam current measured by the last BCM (coloured markers, right Y scale, mA) located just before the beam destination for the [MEBT BCM2, DTL4 BPM SM] pair. The colour of the markers follows the cluster colours as given in Figure 6.

5.2.2.2 K-shape clustering results

For most time-series pairs, the Elbow graph exhibits a clear "elbow" shape providing a precise cluster count. However, for the timeseries pairs that include BPM phase magnitude the elbow shape sometimes is not very clear. Other methods could be used to improve clustering results in this case, such as the Silhouette method[34]. This method provides concise graphical representation of consistency within the clusters of data. The silhouette value ranges between -1 and +1 and is a measure of how similar a cluster element is to its own cluster compared to the other clusters where a high value indicates that the object is well matched to its own cluster and poorly matched to the other clusters. If many elements have a high value, then the clustering configuration is appropriate. The Silhouette method is often found to work well in cases where the Elbow method fails to exhibit a distinct elbow inflection. In addition to this, in case of Silhouette method the optimal k value determination can be automated in contrast to the Elbow method where the optimal k value is extracted visually.

Overall, in this dataset the clustering gives similar results throughout the timeseries combination, resulting in the same events detected in most combinations. The main events are summarised below for specific examples.

Figure 26 shows the clustering results for [DTL4 BCM, DTL4 BPM1 SM] timeseries pair with optimal value of 7 clusters. The following observations can be extracted from this figure:

- **Event 1:** As in the case of single timeseries clustering, the main goal of identifying distinctive timeseries shapes (clusters) appearing prior to the interlocks was not achieved as there is no

clear correlation between the timeseries prior to the interlocks in the given dataset (see events 1 on Figure 26). The observation holds for all time-series pairs used in this study.

- Events 2 and 2.1: The k-shape algorithm shows the capability to identify beam pulse shapes that correlate to the average beam current measured by the DTL4 BCM (see events 2 in Figure 26, although there are no apparent visual differences in the centroid time-series. However, the correlation is not detected in all cases. For example, at event 2.1 in the same figure, one can observe similar average current step patterns without the distinction in time-series shapes. Note that the beam pulse length at event 2.1 was longer (50 μ s) compared to the event 2 (5 μ s) indicating higher degree of beam pulse shape similarity for longer pulses.
- Event 4 and 3: Majority of the beam pulse shapes in the whole data set correspond to the 2 clusters with centroids shown under event 4 on Figure 26. At the start of a new run the beam shape typically exhibits an unusual/faulty shape in BPM SM series.

Figure 26: Clustering results for [DTL4 BCM, DTL4 BPM1 SM] time-series pair with an optimal value of 7 clusters. The events discussed in the text are labelled with numbers and marked with arrows.

Figure 27 summarises the clustering results for the [DTL4 BCM, MEBT BPM3 SA] pair. Here one can observe a change in beam pulse shape in the middle of a run (event 1 on Figure 27) most likely indicating that the clustering detects a change in certain settings influencing this particular BCM and BPM SA pair pulse shape. To identify the underlying setting change requires further work focused on correlating the result with other type of data than used in this study.

Figure 27: Clustering results for [DTL4 BCM, MEBT BPM3 SA] timeseries pair with optimal value of 10 clusters with centroid timeseries (bottom) and plot of interlock and average DTL4 BCM beam current time evolution in the dataset under study (top). The events discussed in the text are labelled with numbers and marked with arrows.

The BPM sum phase (SA) timeseries exhibit stronger inherent noise outside the beam pulse region, which impedes the optimal cluster count determination. In the case of single timeseries the clustering works well for the BPM sum magnitude (SM) timeseries, however the optimal K-value is less distinctive in the case of BPM sum phase (SA) timeseries. In case of timeseries pairs the clustering of 2 BPM SM works slightly worse compared to single BPM SM clustering with typical optimal cluster count of 4-8 and 4-6, respectively. On the other hand, pairing BPM sum magnitude and sum phase timeseries significantly improves the clustering (more distinct clusters with clearer elbow inflection, with optimal K typically on the order of 10) compared to the single BPM SA clustering. Pairing 2 BPM SA timeseries results in even worse clustering (even less clear elbow inflection) as in the case of single BPM SA timeseries clustering.

As the above combinations did not show any distinct clusters prior to beam interlocks, an additional set of timeseries was tested, namely BPM X and Y position data. List of time-series pairs used for this study is given in Table 3. The results were found to be similar to the previous results, with no distinct shapes prior to the interlock (see Figure 28).

Table 3: List of timeseries pairs used to explore the option of time-series pairs with BPM X and Y signals instead of SA and SM.

DTL4 BCM	DTL4 BPM1 X
DTL4 BCM	DTL4 BPM Y
MEBT BCM2	DTL4 BPM1 X

MEBT BCM2	DTL4 BPM1 Y
DTL4 BCM	MEBT BPM3 X
DTL4 BCM	MEBT BPM3 Y

Figure 28: Clustering results with the [DTL4 BCM, MEBT BPM3 Y] timeseries pair.

5.3 CLUSTERING WITH MULTIPLE DATASETS WITH REFINED FILTER ON TIME-SERIES SELECTION

The study described in the previous sections was focused on a single dataset recorded during a 13-hour long stability run. As it did not result in distinct beam pulse shapes prior to beam interlocks, the search space was expanded to other datasets together covering about 2 weeks of data (Start time=2023-06-28 22:00, End time=2023-07-11 10:05). The time-series used in the clustering step were filtered according to the following criteria:

- The average current measured by DTL4 BCM was required to be above 1 mA for each machine cycle to be included in a dataset.
- The beam interlock was raised at the last machine cycle with beam pulse present in each data set.
- A maximum of 50 machine cycles (with beam present) prior to cycle with beam interlock raised were included in each dataset.

As in the study described in previous section, the clustering results with extended data space did not show any apparently distinct clusters/pulse shapes prior to beam interlocks.

5.4 FUTURE ANALYSIS

Based on the results presented in this section, plans include further exploration of clustering 2 or more time-series of mixed data types (different measurements from the same or from different systems) and extending the data space, particularly including RF cavity signals and the additional beam instrumentation systems listed in Section 2.2. In addition to this, other methods for optimal cluster value extraction—which in contrast to Elbow method, can be automated—are planned, in particular, the Silhouette method.

6 ML on the Low Latency Platform

6.1 MAIN FPGA ARCHITECTURE

The Versal Adaptive Compute Acceleration Platform (ACAP) is a new way of working when it comes to FPGA design. It is made up of FPGA logic regions interconnected with a re-programmable Network-on-Chip (NoC). This is part of the Vitis Platform methodology which means that part of the design is reconfigurable ("programmable") through software (SW). This is the initial architecture drafted for the Versal (main FPGA) firmware is shown in **Error! Reference source not found..** Note that this version covers the prototype, so has 8 optical link inputs.

Figure 29: Versal architecture overview

As mentioned earlier the methodology is split across two tools. Hence, the design is split in two parts, shown as dashed lines in the **Error! Reference source not found.:**

- **Hardware Platform:** Built out of "regular" VHDL and AMD block diagrams and IP blocks using a traditional development flow. The output for this is a definition that can be used in the Vitis SW flow.
- **Software Reconfigurable:** Processing "kernels" that can be either in PL or in the dedicated accelerators. The flow diagram (decides the NoC configuration) can be changed through SW.

The overview of the flow in the diagram is the following:

1. Waveforms and data from different systems are received over the optical links and are routed to the reconfigurable NoC.
2. The Optical input Decoding Kernels is high level synthesis code which takes the input stream from the optical links and reformats it into streams suitable for the AI kernels.
3. Optionally, the decoding kernels can write waveform data to the DDR memory for analysis and debugging.
4. The AI Kernels run the ML model inference on the waveform streams.

5. The AI Kernels' output is still to be determined. This part of the design is SW reconfigurable so the result could be sent both to DDR memory for visual inspection or as messages to the GPIO block to set output signals in case of interesting events or critical events.

The following sections describe the subcomponents in a bit more detail.

6.1.1 SFP+ FMC

This component contains the code specific for the FMC. In this case we will have all the actual packet processing in a software reconfigurable part. Therefore, in the HDL part we will need 4 AMD Aurora IPs connected to the correct FMC pins and with the correct clocking setup to match the transmitters. To note is that the 4 IPs will be using the same clock source, which means that the 4 instances of Aurora will need to run at the same speed.

6.1.2 GPIO FMC

The FMC listed here has 5 programmable input/output ports. Not shown on the diagram in Figure 29 is that the GPIO block will have a register bank accessible from the CPU to make static setups, i.e., if a port is going to be used as input or as output. For now, it is assumed that we will send AXIS messages to set the output triggers high in case of an event. We foresee that:

- One pin is used for DoD instrument requests and could be connected to EVR TTL input.
- One or two pins are used for interlock and could be connected to the Fast Beam Interlock System (FBIS). FBIS handles the suppression of beam production once a request for beam inhibit is received.
- The rest of the pins could be used for Event Receiver (EVR) event inputs if we need to act on timing events.

6.1.3 NoC

The network-on-chip interconnect is a big reconfigurable interconnect structure, which is set up on device boot. The NoC supports multiple types of streams and can be used for both transporting address-requested items as well as statically routed streams of data. In our case we will utilize the statically routed streams to pass data from SFP+ FMC → decoding kernels → AI engines. One thing to note is that the NoC is not built of FPGA logic.

6.1.4 Optical Input Decoding Kernels

This logic is expected to be written as HLS and could in theory be moved to the SFP+ FMC hierarchy, but writing the logic in the SW reconfigurable region should provide flexibility. For now, these units are responsible for de-interleaving the data from the optical links. The details regarding the protocol are not finalised yet, but the assumption is that the data is separated into streams belonging to each instrument and pass these on to the ML model input layer. Another option is to let each kernel have

a Master AXI port to be able to reach main memory in which it could write the incoming data streams so we can verify that the data transferred is ok compared to the individual systems.

6.1.5 AI kernels

These are built-in processing kernels from the ACAP. For more details on the hardware see Versal component documentation [37]. The FPGA contains 400 AI kernels which each is basically a combination of a small RISC processor, and a big vector multiply unit for both fixed or floating point as well as 32 kb of RAM and the possibility to move data in and out of the kernel. The cores themselves can run up to 1.3 GHz. How the ML model maps to the AI kernels and the efficiency will be part of the ML model integration.

6.2 WORKING WITH ML MODELS

There are a couple of different ways of working with the SW configurable part of the FPGA. The bulk is to build processing graphs. This can be done by hand or by running an AI compiler for complex models. The code written can be a mix of code that runs on AI kernels or HLS code that runs in the programmable logic.

Figure 30: Versal AI core graph example in Vitis software

Figure 30 shows an example of a processing graph from the AI engine API [38] and is part of the examples of how to work with the Versal architecture. The darker box in the image is the programmable logic and, in this case, it contains code written in HLS:

- MM2S – Memory to streaming interface
- Polar clip – Clips complex input based on threshold
- S2MM – Stream to Memory interface

The light blue box represents the AI kernels where the buf0/1/2 represents the local memory of the kernel which is used as FIFO buffering for the data exchanged between kernels. Note that in this example the kernels are not made from an AI compiler, instead they are small C++ programs with DSP style processing.

- Interpolator – up-sampling FIR filter with 16 coefficients.
- Classifier – Determines quadrant of the incoming polar coordinates.

How the developed models will be partitioned and deployed on the system is still under investigation. But the initial idea is presented in the architecture earlier that the incoming optical links feeds HLS cores that converts the data into a suitable format. Then this is fed to the first layer of the ML model. Worst case a model can be manually split and crafted into a processing graph, but this would be very cumbersome and maybe not that big of an advantage.

The AI compiler is focused around CNNs and supports libraries like Caffe and TensorFlow. The AI compiler framework is described in the Vitis AI documentation [39]. The workflow contains a number of stages:

- Model inspector - initial sanity check to confirm that the operators and sequence of operators in the graph is compatible with Vitis AI.
- Model optimization - exploits the notion of sparsity to reduce the overall computational complexity for inference.
- Model quantization – Make the usage more efficient through the use of integer quantization to reduce the energy cost, memory footprint, and data path bandwidth required for inference.
- Model compilation - construct an internal computation graph as an intermediate representation and maps it to AI kernels.

How to integrate a compiled model using this flow and combine it with manually built graphs into the full system is another question that requires more investigation. There are some examples of Whole Application Acceleration (WAA) based around receiving images via camera on Versal platforms and using programmable logic for pre-processing like resizing and mean subtractions after which its stores the pixels directly to an AI kernel which is the first node of a Resnet50 classifier.

The assessments described in this section validate the choice of FPGA components and system architecture. We expect that MODAL will be a suitable platform for intra-pulse signal communication throughout the facility and the VERSAL FPGA with its toolchain should support appropriate classifiers. Testing at ESS is scheduled to begin in March 2025 in parallel with the start of beam commissioning of the entire ESS linac. That said, experience has shown that demonstration of predictive capability will require stable operation of the linac that will only occur after initial commissioning. We anticipate that significant effort in data analysis and model verification will also be required to demonstrate this capability.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

Over the course of nearly four years, Task 10.6 has explored the potential of low-latency Machine Learning (ML) techniques to improve the performance and availability of high-power hadron accelerators, specifically at the ESS. The task focused on algorithms that could discriminate between classes of beam pulses based on subtle differences in the measured current, phase and position. These show some promise in achieving the ultimate goal of identifying errant beam conditions in real-time and implementing ML algorithms to protect the accelerator. The ESS linac provided valuable data for this study, and the architecture of a low-latency platform utilizing Field-programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) has been established.

Currently, the realization of this low-latency platform at a scale suitable for the entire ESS accelerator is now being supported by the ESS and the Polish Ministry of Science. Similarly, enhancements to the data workflow have been motivated by I.FAST Task 10.6 experience, and development is now being carried forward by a team within the ESS Integrated Control System Division. The clustering studies on signals from beam current, position, and phase have demonstrated shape discrimination, but more data from stable operations is needed for robust identification of precursors to anomalous beam conditions. We expect that upcoming ESS operations will provide the necessary conditions and that workflows developed during Task 10.6 will enable exploitation of the resulting data.

Throughout the project, the Task 10.6 team has benefited from and contributed to related activities within I.FAST and throughout a growing collaboration of AI practitioners in the European accelerator community[25][40]. In addition, ESS and the US Department of Energy's Oak Ridge National Laboratory have signed a bilateral agreement covering ML development. As Task 10.6 efforts conclude and follow-on work commences, we intend to strengthen these relationships.

Upcoming steps include deployment of the low-latency platform at ESS and the implementation of relevant ML algorithms on the selected Versal FPGA. With the commissioning of the ESS linac commencing in Spring 2025, the collaborators are well-positioned with tools for data acquisition, analysis, and ML implementation. The expected positive impact extends to other high-power hadron facilities in Europe and beyond, paving the way for advancements in accelerator applications of machine learning.

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9 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ACAP	Adaptive Compute Acceleration Platform
ACCT(s)	AC Current Transformer(s)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMD	Advanced Micro Devices (previously Xilinx)
AMC	Advanced Mezzanine Card
BCM	Beam Current Monitor
BE	Back End
BLM	Beam Loss Monitor
BNL	Brookhaven National Laboratory
BPM	Beam Position Monitor
CLK	Clock
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
DoD	Data-on-Demand
DPU	Deep-learning Processor Unit
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
DTL	Drift Tube Linac
EPICS	Experimental Physics and Industrial Control System
PV	Process Variable
ESS	European Spallation Source
EU	European Union
FC	Faraday Cup
FBIS	Fast Beam Interlock System
FE	Front End
FCT	Fast Current Transformer
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FW	Firmware
GSPs	Gigasamples per second
GB	Gigabytes

GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format, version 5
HEBT	High Energy Beta Transfer
HW	Hardware
IB(s)	Insertable Beam Stop(s)
ICBLM	Ionization Chamber Based Beam Loss Monitor
ID	Identifier
IF	Intermediate Frequency
IFAST	Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
IOC(s)	Input/Output Controller(s)
IP	Intellectual Property
ISrc	Ion Source
IT	Intelligent Trigger
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LEBT	Low Energy Beam Transport
LINAC	Linear Accelerator
LLRF	Low-Level RF
MCU	Micro-controller Unit
MEBT	Medium Energy Beam Transport
ML	Machine Learning
MODAL	Minimum-latency Optical Data Acquisition Link
MRF	Micro Research Finland
MSPS	Megasamples per second
MSU	Michigan State University
MTCA	MicroTCA
nBLM	Neutron Sensitive Beam Loss Monitor
NC	Normal Conducting
NCL	Normal Conducting Linac
NoC	Network-on-Chip
NOK	Not OK
NT	Normative Types
PV(s)	Process Variable(s)
PM	

QSFP	Quad Small Form-factor Pluggable
RF	Radio Frequency
RFQ	Radio Frequency Quadrupole
ROI	Region of Interest
RTV	Riga Technical University
SC	Superconducting
SCL	Superconducting Linac
SDS	Synchronous Data Service
SFP	Small Form-factor
SLAC	Stanford Linear Accelerator Centre
SNS	Spallation Neutron Source, Oak Ridge, TN
SW	Software
TS	Timing System
VHDL	VHIC (Very High-Speed Integrated Circuit) Hardware Description Language
WUT	Warsaw University of Technology